

Original Research

Factors Influencing Generation Z's Mobile Banking Adoption in Indonesia: Integrating UTAUT and DOI Theories

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Abstract

The rapid growth of digital technology has changed banking behavior, especially among Generation Z. Although internet penetration in Indonesia has reached 79.5% and 'mobile banking' transactions have increased by 68.5%, adoption among Generation Z has not been widely studied. This study investigates the factors influencing the intention to use 'mobile banking' among Generation Z in Indonesia by integrating the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) with the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory. Data was collected from 301 Generation Z respondents, 78.4% of whom were female, using non-probability sampling techniques and analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling–Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS). The results indicate that performance expectancy ($\beta = 0.403$, $p = 0.000$), effort expectancy ($\beta = 0.216$, $p = 0.004$), and facilitating conditions ($\beta = 0.163$, $p = 0.041$) significantly influence the intention to use 'mobile banking'. Meanwhile, perceived trust, perceived security, and relative advantage did not have a significant effect. The integration of relative advantage from DOI enriches UTAUT by adding a dimension of innovative perception toward technology. These findings suggest that developers and financial institutions should focus on providing user-friendly interface designs and reliable infrastructure to enhance adoption among digital users. Further research is recommended to consider gender as a moderating variable and use more balanced sampling techniques to improve the generalizability of the results.

Keywords: DOI, generation Z, Indonesia, mobile banking, PLS-SEM, technology adoption, UTAUT.

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Introduction

The development of technology, information and communication has brought major changes, especially in the banking service sector (Dhingra & Gupta, 2020). Manual banking is starting to be abandoned by customers along with the rapid development of technology, while digital banking such as ‘mobile banking’ is in demand because it offers convenience and speed in transactions (Dendrinis & Spais, 2024). Banks or financial institutions provide various services to their customers, including fund transfers, digital payments, monetary transactions, and account balance inquiries. ‘Mobile banking’ apps can be accessed on mobile devices anytime and anywhere (Nguyen & Dao, 2024). Banks also benefit from ‘mobile banking’. Banks can optimize operational costs and provide quality banking services to customers at large (Merhi et al., 2019).

In recent years, ‘mobile banking’ apps have gained significant popularity as they offer users a convenient and safe method to handle their financial matters. It has changed the way customers conduct financial transactions and has brought about a revolution in the banking industry (Behera et al., 2023). This has resulted in many banks closing their branch offices to switch to digital-based banking services. Data from the Financial Services Authority shows that as of September 2024 a number of banks in Indonesia have closed as many as 23,935 commercial bank office units. This number has decreased by 524 units on an annualized basis compared to the previous year and down by 37 units from the previous month.

‘Mobile banking’ is one of the most significant innovations in the banking sector, especially with the increase in internet usage in Indonesia. The Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII) reported that the number of internet users in Indonesia in 2024 will reach 79.5% or 221,563,479 people. This number shows an increase of 1.4% compared to the previous year. Bank Indonesia data in 2024 shows that the volume of ‘mobile banking’ transactions was recorded at 14.09 billion, an increase of 68.5% from the previous year. The transaction value in 2024 was recorded at Rp 16,725 trillion, an increase of 71.8%. This increase shows that the importance of using ‘mobile banking’ in facilitating the management of financial transactions of its users (Abu-Taieh et al., 2022).

In the midst of this digital transformation, Generation Z, born between 1997 and 2012, has become a key factor. This group grew up in a digital environment, accustomed to app-based services such as QRIS, e-wallets, and online savings accounts. Seabank, for example, has successfully captured 57% of the Gen Z digital banking market share thanks to its simple and efficient interface (Media Indonesia, 2024). However, despite its high usage, there is still limited research specifically exploring the factors influencing Gen Z's intention to adopt ‘mobile banking’ in Indonesia. Previous studies such as Abdennebi (2023) and Belmonte, et al (2024) have focused on older generations or have not differentiated behavior based on generational segmentation. Yet, Generation Z has its own unique perceptions regarding trust, risk, and the innovative value of a technology.

This study aims to fill this gap by analyzing the intention to use ‘mobile banking’ among Generation Z in Indonesia, which is influenced by various factors. The main theory used in this study is the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology

(UTAUT) (Pourghanbari et al., 2022). Numerous research efforts have employed the UTAUT theory to examine individual behavior in adopting technology and provide greater insight into the advantages of this theory over previous theories (Asrori & Amal, 2023). UTAUT theory detects that effort expectancy, performance expectancy, facilitating conditions, perceived trust, and perceived security are considerations in adopting 'mobile banking'. However, this theory has not fully captured the dimension of innovation perception, particularly for Generation Z, who are known to be adaptive to new technologies and highly consider the comparative benefits of a digital service.

To that end, this study integrates the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory as a complement to UTAUT. DOI emphasizes the importance of innovation attributes such as relative advantage, which is the perception that new technology provides an advantage over older methods (Anh, 2023). In the context of 'mobile banking', relative advantage is a crucial factor because this service offers efficiency, convenience, and flexibility that align with the characteristics of Generation Z. Therefore, the integration of these two theories is believed to capture both user behavior and perceptions of the innovative value of technology, thereby providing a more comprehensive analysis in understanding Generation Z's intentions in Indonesia to use 'mobile banking' services. Although UTAUT includes moderators such as age and gender, this study does not directly explore the role of moderators because the sample used is homogeneous in terms of generation. However, this analysis still provides important insights into the dynamics of financial technology adoption by young users in Indonesia and offers practical implications for digital banking service providers in designing strategies based on the behavior of future generations.

The adoption of 'mobile banking' by Generation Z in Indonesia is influenced by several key factors. Effort Expectancy describes the ease of use of the application, where the easier it is to use, the higher the individual's interest in using it (Venkatesh et al., 2003). According to Dhingra & Gupta (2020), 'mobile banking' will be highly recognized if people realize that using this service makes their banking activities easy and simple. Performance Expectancy shows the belief that 'mobile banking' can improve the efficiency of financial management, which drives user intentions. In addition, Facilitating Conditions, such as internet access and adequate technical support, are also important factors in increasing the use of 'mobile banking' (Purwanto & Loisa, 2020).

The intention to use 'mobile banking' is also influenced by several other factors. Perceived trust is an important factor in influencing the intention to use 'mobile banking'. Users will adopt new technology if the technology can be trusted (Nawi et al., 2024). However, there is a major threat in the application of 'mobile banking', namely the risk of leakage of users' personal data due to hacker attacks (Merhi et al., 2019). Therefore, banks need to prioritize perceived security by protecting and guaranteeing users' personal data while using 'mobile banking' (Abdennebi, 2023). In addition to security aspects, users tend to apply digital banking innovations that offer relative advantages to improve efficiency, effectiveness and operations (Chen et al., 2023). For innovations to be widely implemented, they must have relative advantages compared to previous technologies (Tiwari et al., 2023).

Previous research on the effect of effort expectancy on technology use provides mixed results, indicating that this factor has a different impact according to the technology used. In a study conducted by Dendrinis & Spais (2024) found that effort expectancy has a significant effect on behavioral intentions to the adoption of 'mobile banking'. Similar results were also shown in the research of Li'ebana-Cabanillas, et al (2024) which concluded that effort expectancy significantly affects the intention to use biometric m-payment systems. In addition, research by Islam, et al (2024) confirms that effort expectancy has a significant effect on intention to use QR mobile payments. However, some studies show different results. In research conducted by Sulistyowati, et al (2021) found that effort expectancy does not have a significant effect on intention to use 'mobile banking'. Similar results were also shown in the research of Tariq, et al (2024) which concluded that effort expectancy has no significant effect on actual usage of fintech. In addition, research by Valle, et al (2024) confirms that effort expectancy has no significant effect on behavioral intention to use AI.

In addition to effort expectancy, performance expectancy research on technology use also provides mixed results. According to a study carried out by Abu-Taieh, et al (2022) found that performance expectancy has a significant effect on the behavioral intention of customers to use m-banking services. In addition, research by Anwar & Alviayatun (2022) found that performance expectancy significantly affects mobile wallet adoption. Furthermore, Rana, et al (2024) reported that performance expectancy has a significant effect on intention to adopt AI. However, not all studies support these findings. In a study conducted by Dhingra & Gupta (2020) found that performance expectancy does not have a significant effect on behavioral intention to use 'mobile banking'. In addition, research by Hassan, et al (2023) found that performance expectancy has no significant effect on behavioral intention to use fintech services. Furthermore, Sebasti'an (2023) reported that performance expectancy has no significant effect on user's intention for using Bizum P2P system.

Facilitating conditions are also one of the factors that influence technology use. In research conducted by Dendrinis & Spais (2024) found that facilitating conditions have a significant effect on behavior intentions to the adoption of 'mobile banking'. Similar results were also shown in research Asrori & Amal (2023) which concluded that facilitating conditions significantly affect behavior intention to use DAL. In addition, research by Rana, et al (2024) revealed that facilitating conditions have a significant effect on intention to adopt AI. However, different results were found by other studies. In research conducted by Abu-Taieh, et al (2022) found that facilitating conditions do not have a significant effect on the behavioral intention of customers to use m-banking services. Similar results were also shown in the research of Islam, et al (2024) which concluded that facilitating conditions have no significant effect on the intention to use QR mobile payments. In addition, research by Valle, et al (2024) revealed that facilitating conditions have no significant effect on behavioral intention to use AI.

In a similar context, numerous earlier investigations examining the influence of perceived trust on technology adoption have yielded varied results. In research conducted by Belmonte, et al (2024) found that perceived trust has a significant effect on intention to use e-wallet. Similar results were also shown in the study conducted by Ahmed, et al (2024) which concluded that perceived trust significantly affects behavioral intention to

use cybernetic payment network services. Furthermore, Nirmawan & Astiwardhani (2021) revealed that perceived trust has a significant effect on the intention to use go-pay mobile payment. However, several other studies have found different results. In research conducted by Abdennebi (2023) found that trust has no significant effect on m-banking adoption intention.

In addition, findings regarding the effect of perceived security on technology use provide mixed results. In research conducted by Belmonte, et al (2024) found that perceived security has a significant effect on intention to use e-wallet. This is in line with research by Xu, et al (2025) which reports that perceived security significantly affects Chinese guests' intentions to use WeChat pay or Alipay. Furthermore, Sudono, et al (2020) established that the feeling of security greatly influences the desire to utilize mobile payment. However, other studies have come to different conclusions. In research conducted by Abdennebi (2023) found that perceived security has no significant effect on m-banking adoption intention. This is in line with the research of Islam, et al (2024) which concluded that perceived security has no significant effect on intention to use QR mobile payments.

On the other hand, studies on the effect of relative advantage on technology use provide mixed findings. In a study conducted by Anh (2023) it was revealed that the concept of relative advantage plays a crucial role in the adoption of 'mobile banking'. Similar results were also shown in Elbayoumy & Ding (2023) indicating that relative advantage notably influences 'mobile banking' adoption. In addition, a study by Februadi, et al (2025) indicated that relative advantage notably impacts the intention to adopt mobile business applications. However, some studies show conflicting results. Research by Hamzah, et al (2023) indicated that relative advantage does not significantly influence the adoption of cloud accounting. Similar results were also shown in research by Chen, et al (2023) which concluded that relative advantage has no significant effect on cloud computing adoption.

This research aims to examine the intention to use 'mobile banking' by considering variables such as effort expectancy, performance expectancy, facilitating conditions, perceived trust, perceived security, and relative advantage. These factors reflect the functional, psychological, and perceptual aspects of Generation Z's innovative technology values in making decisions to adopt 'mobile banking'. The theoretical approach used combines UTAUT to capture behavioral factors influencing usage intention, along with DOI to complement the framework with dimensions of innovation perception. Thus, this study is expected to enrich the academic literature on technology adoption behavior among generations and provide practical contributions for digital financial service providers in designing strategies aligned with the needs and preferences of Generation Z in the evolving digital banking era.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) theory was developed by Venkatesh, et al (2003) to understand the main factors that influence

individual intention and behavior in adopting new technology. This theory is the result of integrating eight existing technology adoption frameworks, including the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), and produces four main constructs: performance expectations, social influence, effort expectations, and facilitating conditions, as well as four moderators: age, experience, gender, and voluntary use (Dendrinis & Spais, 2024). Although UTAUT includes four moderators, this study did not evaluate the role of these moderators because all respondents came from a relatively homogeneous generational group. However, this justification aligns with research by Al-Adwan, et al (2024), which states that excluding moderators is acceptable when the sample is demographically controlled. The advantage of UTAUT lies in its broader coverage of behavioral constructs and its ability to explain both users' intentions and actual behavior. Compared to TAM and TPB, UTAUT is more comprehensive as it incorporates dimensions such as facilitating conditions and effort expectancy, which are relevant to the digital context.

UTAUT provides a very effective model for understanding how technology is accepted, both by individuals and organizations, thus becoming a widely used theoretical framework (Williams et al., 2015). In this study, the UTAUT framework is expanded by adding additional variables such as perceived trust and perceived security, with a focus on generation Z in Indonesia as a potential user group in the application of 'mobile banking'. This development is in line with various previous studies that also add factors such as perceived trust to UTAUT, because these factors have an important role in understanding the process of adopting new technology (Slade et al., 2015). Therefore, through the UTAUT theory, this study will examine the effect of variables such as effort expectancy, performance expectancy, facilitating conditions, perceived trust and perceived security on the intention to use 'mobile banking' as a new technology.

Although UTAUT is widely used to predict behavioral intentions, this theory is considered to lack the ability to capture the aspect of innovation, which is an important factor in the adoption of digital technology, especially for digital-native generations such as Generation Z. Therefore, this study integrates the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory to complement the UTAUT analytical framework. DOI, developed by Rogers (1962), highlights the process of innovation diffusion and emphasizes important attributes such as relative advantage, which is the perception that an innovation has an advantage over previous methods (Elbayoumy & Ding, 2023). In the context of 'mobile banking', relative advantage is important because Generation Z is highly responsive to technologies that offer greater efficiency, flexibility, and accessibility. Generation Z tends to choose digital services like QRIS and Seabank due to their efficiency and smooth app design (Belmonte et al., 2024). Recent studies, such as Anh (2023), Ayanwale & Ndlovu (2024), and Februadi, et al (2025), indicate that combining UTAUT and DOI can provide a more comprehensive understanding of technology adoption, particularly in digital financial services. This combined approach is considered capable of capturing both user behavior aspects (through UTAUT) and perceptions of technologically innovative value (through DOI), thereby producing a stronger and more relevant analysis in explaining Generation Z's intentions to use 'mobile banking' in Indonesia.

On the other hand, previous studies have shown mixed results. For example, Dendrinis & Spais (2024) in Greece used PLS-SEM and found that effort expectancy was significant

for intention, while Sulistyowati, et al (2021) in Indonesia found the opposite result. This difference may be due to users' familiarity with digital technology, which means that ease of use is no longer the main determinant. Additionally, most previous studies were cross-sectional and descriptive in nature, and therefore unable to capture long-term behavioral changes (Behera et al., 2023). Studies focusing on the Indonesian context, especially those targeting Generation Z specifically, are still very limited. Therefore, this study not only combines UTAUT and DOI as complementary analytical frameworks but also contributes to filling the empirical gap by targeting Indonesia's digital-native population, who have unique preferences regarding the adoption of financial technology.

Hypothesis Development

Effort expectancy and intention to use 'mobile banking'

Venkatesh, et al (2003) characterize effort expectancy as "the degree of simplicity linked to employing the system". Pertaining to 'mobile banking', Thusi & Maduku (2020) elaborate on effort expectancy as the extent of user assurance that 'mobile banking' applications are straightforward to comprehend and demand minimal effort in their operation. By utilizing the technology that users already have and the ease of operation, this application is able to create a sense of comfort for its users (Cokins et al., 2020). However, even though 'mobile banking' applications offer various benefits, some consumers are still reluctant to use them due to the difficulty in taking the time and effort required to learn new technology (Ivanova & Kim, 2022). This is in line with the research of Hidayatullah, et al (2020) which found that effort expectancy has a significant effect on behavioral intention to use 'mobile banking'. Similar results were also shown in the research of Abu-Taieh, et al (2022) which reported that effort expectancy has a significant effect on the behavioral intention of Customers to use m-banking service. In addition, research by Al-Adwan, et al (2024) confirmed that effort expectancy has a significant effect on metaverse commerce adoption intention. Consequently, the hypothesis is put forward:

H₁: Effort expectancy has a significant effect on intention to use 'mobile banking'

Performance expectancy and intention to use 'mobile banking'

Venkatesh, et al (2003) define performance expectancy as "the level of individual confidence that the use of the system will increase effectiveness and provide benefits to their performance". Performance expectations refer to the extent to which a person believes that the use of information systems can improve their performance (Cokins et al., 2020). In this case, 'mobile banking' services allow users to carry out financial transactions anytime and anywhere, thus improving their performance by providing a fast, flexible and convenient process (Dhingra & Gupta, 2020). This is in line with the research of Islam, et al (2024) who found that performance expectancy has a significant effect on intention to use QR mobile payments. Similar results are also shown in the research of Tariq, et al (2024) which states that performance expectancy substantially influences the actual utilization of fintech innovation. Moreover, research by Dendrinis & Spais (2024) confirms that performance expectancy significantly impacts on behavior intentions to the adoption of 'mobile banking'. Consequently, the hypothesis is put forward:

H₂: Performance expectancy has a significant effect on intention to use ‘mobile banking’

Facilitating condition and intention to use ‘mobile banking’

Venkatesh, et al (2003) define facilitating condition as “the level of a person's belief that the necessary organization and infrastructure are available to support system use”. In the realm of ‘mobile banking’, this implies that users should possess adequate knowledge and access to supportive infrastructure to carry out banking services effectively (Ivanova & Kim, 2022). This must be accompanied by good ‘mobile banking’ facilities, such as technology, features, and services that make it easier for consumers to conduct financial transactions. These factors greatly influence consumers' intention to open an account and utilize the services provided by the bank. In addition, this is also an important consideration for consumers to start adopting technology in financial transactions (Yuliana & Aprianingsih, 2022). This aligns with the findings of Achmadi, et al (2024) found that facilitating conditions have a significant effect on behavioral intention. Similar results are also shown in the research of Paramita & Cahyadi (2024) which states that facilitating conditions have a significant effect on behavioral intention to use QRIS. In addition, research by Xu, et al (2025) found that facilitating conditions have a significant effect on Chinese Guests' Intentions to Use (INT) WeChat Pay or Alipay. Consequently, the hypothesis is put forward:

H₃: Facilitating condition has a significant effect on intention to use ‘mobile banking’

Perceived trust and intention to use ‘mobile banking’

Perceived trust is an individual's belief that the technology offered is able to secure and protect the personal data of its users (Nawi et al., 2024). In the context of ‘mobile banking’, users must disclose personal and financial information to ‘mobile banking’ services, so data security and privacy are key considerations in building user trust (Ashrafi et al., 2022). Trust can also be understood as a psychological prerequisite within the UTAUT framework that strengthens the relationship between performance expectancy and behavioral intention, as trust creates an initial sense of security before evaluating functional aspects (Ahmed et al., 2024). This is in line with the research of Abu-Taieh, et al (2022) which found that perceived trust has a significant effect on the behavioral intention of customers to use m-banking services. Similar results were also shown in the research of Ezeudoka & Mingyue (2024) which concluded that perceived trust significantly affects the intention to use e-pharmacy. In addition, research by Nawi, et al (2024) validated that the perceived trust influences the willingness to adopt e-wallets. Consequently, the hypothesis is put forward:

H₄: Perceived trust has a significant effect on intention to use ‘mobile banking’

Perceived security and intention to use ‘mobile banking’

Perceived security means that users feel safe in using ‘mobile banking’, because they believe that the ‘mobile banking’ system will protect users' personal and financial data from misuse (Abdennebi, 2023). Perceived security is a logical expansion of facilitating

conditions in UTAUT for the context of financial technology. Security is positioned as an emotional infrastructure enabler that allows individuals to feel comfortable using the system (Belmonte et al., 2024). Therefore, the greater the sense of perceived security, the stronger the likelihood of engaging in ‘mobile banking’ (Sudono et al., 2020). This aligns with the findings of Merhi, et al (2019) which indicated that perceived security significantly influences the behavioral intent to embrace ‘mobile banking’. Corresponding conclusions were also observed in the study by Wong & Mo (2019) which determined that perceived security substantially impacts consumer willingness to utilize mobile payment. In addition, research conducted by Tahar, et al (2020) validates that perceived security meaningfully affects the intention to use e-filing. Consequently, the hypothesis is put forward:

H₅: Perceived security has a significant effect on intention to use ‘mobile banking’

Relative advantage and intention to use ‘mobile banking’

According to Rogers (2010) relative advantage is the level at which an innovation is considered more profitable than the previous technology (Chen et al., 2023). Within the UTAUT framework combined with DOI, relative advantage complements performance expectancy by highlighting the innovative value of a technology. This is particularly important in the context of Generation Z, who are more likely to adopt technologies that are not only practically beneficial but also reflect a digital lifestyle, convenience, and modernity (Ayanwale & Ndlovu, 2024). Therefore, when users perceive ‘mobile banking’ as offering relatively greater innovative value, they are more likely to adopt ‘mobile banking’ in their daily lives (Alshirah et al., 2021). Study of Ayanwale & Ndlovu (2024) revealed that relative advantage play a crucial role in influencing the behavioral intention to utilize chatbots. Likewise, the findings from Tiwari, et al (2023) demonstrated that relative advantage are a significant factor in the adoption of electronic-invoicing. In addition, the study conducted by Lutfi, et al (2022) validated that relative advantage significantly impact the adoption of big data. Consequently, the hypothesis is put forward:

H₆: Relative advantage has a significant effect on intention to use ‘mobile banking’

Figure 1. shows the proposed conceptual framework in this research.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework for ‘Mobile Banking’ Adoption

Methodology

This study uses a quantitative approach with a survey technique via Google Form to collect information about the intention to use ‘mobile banking’. The questionnaire is divided into two parts, namely demographic information and questions for dependent and independent variables measured using a 5-point Likert scale. The variable intention to use ‘mobile banking’ was measured with 4 items (Sulistyowati et al., 2021), effort expectancy was measured with 4 items (Pourghanbari et al., 2022), performance expectancy was measured with 4 items (Dhingra & Gupta, 2020), facilitating conditions were measured with 4 items (Dhingra & Gupta, 2020), perceived trust is measured using 4 items (Nirmawan & Astiwardhani, 2021), perceived security is measured using 3 items (Sudono et al., 2020), and relative advantage is measured using 3 items (Chen et al., 2023).

Respondents of this study are generation Z (born 1997-2012), bank customers, and have devices such as mobile devices to support the use of ‘mobile banking’. A total of 301 valid data were obtained using nonprobability sampling techniques. Recruitment was carried out through social media platforms targeting Generation Z in various regions of Indonesia. Ethical considerations were addressed through the use of digital consent forms, anonymous data collection, and encrypted data storage. Most of the respondents were female (236 respondents, or 78.4%) and 65 male respondents (21.6%). The majority of respondents were unmarried (279 respondents, or 92.7%), over 20 years old (264 respondents, or 87.7%), and a student (218 respondents, or 71.8%). Data analysis was conducted using SmartPLS 4.0 with a Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach, a distribution-free multivariate statistical method used to test relationships between latent variables in a model (Hair et al., 2017).

Results

Table 1 shows the results of discriminant validity testing using the Fornell-Larcker criteria, where the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of each construct is located on the main diagonal and compared with the correlations between other constructs. The results indicate that all AVE values (e.g., Effort Expectancy = 0.844; Performance Expectancy = 0.859; Facilitating Conditions = 0.826) are higher than their correlations with other constructs, meaning that each construct represents itself more than the others. Thus, it can be concluded that all constructs in this study have good discriminant validity, and each variable used in the measurement model successfully captures unique concepts that do not overlap with one another.

Table 1. Fornell-Larckel Criterion for Discriminant Validity

	EE	PE	FC	PT	PS	RA	INT
EE	0.844						
PE	0.726	0.859					
FC	0.751	0.786	0.826				
PT	0.533	0.505	0.557	0.877			
PS	0.411	0.379	0.430	0.732	0.885		
RA	0.544	0.545	0.599	0.495	0.439	0.835	
INT	0.724	0.779	0.742	0.532	0.393	0.570	0.840

Descriptive analysis illustrates the Mean (M) and Standard Deviation (SD) values of each indicator in this study. Based on Table 2, the average value spans from 3.77 to 4.45, while the standard deviation varies between 0.736 and 0.913. These results indicate that respondents tend to have the intention to adopt ‘mobile banking’, because it provides convenience in conducting financial transactions quickly and efficiently. In addition, respondents also feel comfortable and believe that ‘mobile banking’ is safe to use. Not only that, ‘mobile banking’ also contributes to increasing productivity, as it allows users to conduct transactions anytime and anywhere without having to visit the bank in person. Regarding the validity testing of indicators through factor loading values, all indicators have values above the minimum threshold of 0.7. However, indicator RA1 has a loading value of 0.709, and this item is retained due to its theoretical alignment with the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) framework, particularly in measuring perceptions of relative advantage relevant to the context of technology adoption by Generation Z.

Table 2. Loading, cronbach alpha, CR and AVE

Constructs	Items	M	SD	Factor loading (>0.7)	Cronbach alpha (>0.7)	CR (>0.7)	AVE (>0.5)
Effort expectancy (EE)	EE1	4.38	0.736	0.819	0.865	0.908	0.712
	EE2			0.834			
	EE3			0.850			
	EE4			0.871			
Performance expectancy (PE)	PE1	4.45	0.747	0.876	0.881	0.918	0.737
	PE2			0.889			
	PE3			0.841			
	PE4			0.826			
Facilitating condition (FC)	FC1	4.31	0.805	0.826	0.845	0.896	0.682
	FC2			0.831			
	FC3			0.804			
	FC4			0.843			
Perceived trust (PT)	PT1	3.99	0.838	0.884	0.900	0.930	0.769
	PT2			0.859			
	PT3			0.894			
	PT4			0.870			
Perceived security (PS)	PS1	3.77	0.913	0.875	0.864	0.916	0.784
	PS2			0.882			
	PS3			0.899			
Relative advantage (RA)	RA1	4.02	0.897	0.709	0.784	0.872	0.697
	RA2			0.881			
	RA3			0.900			
Intention to use ‘mobile banking’ (INT)	INT1	4.33	0.802	0.873	0.860	0.905	0.705
	INT2			0.844			
	INT3			0.862			
	INT4			0.776			

In the measurement model, Cronbach's Alpha serves to evaluate the internal dependability of a construct. A Cronbach's Alpha value exceeding 0.7 signifies that the items in one construct have good internal consistency to measure the variable. In this study, all constructs have values between 0.784 to 0.900, which means that the indicators in each variable are reliable and the test is successfully fulfilled. In addition to reliability, validity was also tested using Average Variance Extracted (AVE), which serves as an indicator of convergent validity and shows the extent to which latent variables explain the variance of their indicators. All AVE values in this study exceeded the threshold of 0.5, ranging from 0.682 to 0.784, which means that each construct has good convergent validity and indicates that convergent validity has been met.

Figure 2. Structural Model Assessment with Path Coefficients and Significance Values

Figure 2 shows the results of the structural model evaluation, with a coefficient of determination (R²) value of 68.8%, which means that the model is able to explain 68.8% of the variability in intention to use 'mobile banking'. Of the six variables tested, performance expectancy had the strongest influence ($\beta = 0.403$, $p = 0.000$), indicating that perceptions of 'mobile banking' significantly improve financial performance and can drive adoption by up to 40.3%. Additionally, effort expectancy ($\beta = 0.216$, $p = 0.004$) and facilitating conditions ($\beta = 0.163$, $p = 0.041$) also have a significant influence on the intention to use 'mobile banking'. Therefore, hypotheses H1, H2, and H3 are accepted. Conversely, perceived trust ($\beta = 0.099$, $p = 0.165$), perceived security ($\beta = -0.036$, $p = 0.480$), and relative advantage ($\beta = 0.103$, $p = 0.076$) do not have a significant influence on the intention to use 'mobile banking'. Thus, hypotheses H4, H5, and H6 are rejected. Detailed information regarding the coefficient values and significance levels is presented in Table 3 and visualized in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Structural Model Evaluation

Table 3. Structural Model Results with Coefficients and P-values

	Original sample	Sample mean	Standard deviation	T statistics	P values
EE -> INT	0.216	0.206	0.074	2.913	0.004
PE -> INT	0.403	0.404	0.073	5.536	0.000
FC -> INT	0.163	0.164	0.080	2.040	0.041
PT -> INT	0.099	0.103	0.071	1.389	0.165
PS -> INT	-0.036	-0.034	0.051	0.707	0.480
RA -> INT	0.103	0.106	0.058	1.773	0.076

Discussion

This study highlights the factors considered by customers in determining their intention to use ‘mobile banking’ services. The results show that most bank customers in Indonesia, as reflected by the respondents, have a high interest in adopting ‘mobile banking’. The findings from the hypothesis examination reveal that effort expectancy has a significant influence on intention to use ‘mobile banking’ with p-value of 0.004 and a t-statistic of 2.913. These results align with the UTAUT framework and are consistent with the results of research conducted by Dendrinis & Spais (2024) in Greece, which found that effort expectancy has a significant effect on behavioral intention to the adoption of ‘mobile banking’. Likewise Abu-Taieh, et al (2022) in Jordan, showed that effort expectancy significantly impacts customers' inclination to adopt m-banking services. This indicates that as effort expectancy increases, so does their willingness to use ‘mobile banking’. Applications with simple interfaces are more likely to be adopted

by Generation Z, who prefer practical and easy-to-implement systems. In Indonesia, the widespread adoption of QRIS reinforces the role of effort expectancy by simplifying transactions without repetitive processes.

Performance expectancy also shows a very significant effect on intention to use 'mobile banking' with a p-value of 0.000 and a t-statistic of 5,536. This shows that users believe that using 'mobile banking' will improve performance in conducting financial transactions, which in turn increases the intention to use 'mobile banking'. This finding is consistent with the research of Dendrinis & Spais (2024) in Greece, which found that performance expectancy has a significant effect on behavioral intention to the adoption of 'mobile banking'. Likewise, research by Sulistyowati, et al (2021) in Indonesia, which found that performance expectancy has a significant effect on intention to use 'mobile banking'. This suggests that bank customers in Indonesia believe that 'mobile banking' can increase productivity, save time, and speed up financial transactions, such as bill payments or fund transfers. In Indonesia, Seabank's success in capturing 57% of the Gen Z digital banking market reflects that performance expectancy is greatly influenced by responsive app design that aligns with young people's preferences. Thus, performance expectancy is influenced not only by functional benefits but also by responsive app design that aligns with the digital lifestyle of young users.

Facilitating condition show a significant effect on intention to use 'mobile banking' with a p-value of 0.041 and a t-statistic of 2.040. This shows that adequate infrastructure and resource support can affect users' intention to use 'mobile banking'. This study aligns with the findings presented in the research by Dendrinis & Spais (2024) in Greece, which indicated that enabling facilitating conditions greatly influence the intent to embrace 'mobile banking'. In the same vein, a study conducted by Rana, et al (2024) revealed that enabling facilitating conditions a crucial role in the willingness to embrace AI in Bangladesh. This study shows that the presence of adequate facilities such as a stable internet network and technical support, is very important to increase comfort and trust in users' intention to adopt 'mobile banking'. Therefore, the availability of supportive infrastructure, such as a stable internet network is necessary for 'mobile banking' to operate optimally and provide better services for users so that many users are encouraged to adopt and utilize 'mobile banking' effectively.

Perceived trust also has no significant effect on intention to use 'mobile banking' with a p-value of 0.165 and a t-statistic of 1.389. This finding is consistent with Abdennebi (2023) study in Tunisia, which states that trust has no significant influence on m-banking adoption intention. This study reflects a change in Generation Z's attitude toward digital services. This group grew up in the technological era, so trust in digital platforms is considered something that is inherent and no longer a separate consideration (Ashrafi et al., 2022). In Indonesia, 'mobile banking' services are generally provided by large banks with strong reputations, so users tend to "automatically trust" them without re-evaluating the reliability of the system. Additionally, according to Ahmed, et al (2024), for users who are already familiar with technology, trust tends to be a basic expectation rather than a decisive factor in usage decisions.

Perceived security shows insignificant results on intention to use 'mobile banking' with an original sample value of -0.036, a p-value of 0.480, a t-statistic of 0.707. This

finding is consistent with Abdennebi (2023) research in Tunisia which failed to identify the influence of perceived security on m-banking adoption intention. Similarly, Islam, et al (2024) showed that perceived security has no significant effect on intention to use QR mobile payments. Among Generation Z, this may occur because they already consider 'mobile banking' to be a secure service by default, so it is no longer a primary concern. In Indonesia, high trust in large state-regulated banking institutions also reduces users' concerns about potential data breaches (Ahmed et al., 2024). Additionally, overly complex security protocols can reduce user convenience and negatively impact usage intent (Belmonte et al., 2024). Thus, excessive perceived security can disrupt convenience, which is a top priority for Generation Z.

Relative advantage has no significant effect on intention to use 'mobile banking' with a p-value of 0.076 and a t-statistic of 1.773. This could be due to the fact that the advantages offered by 'mobile banking' are not considered to be far superior to other methods that have been used before, such as internet banking, QRIS, or e-wallets. With a high level of digital exposure, Generation Z in Indonesia tends to view 'mobile banking' as part of the standard digital financial services, not as a new innovation that provides significant added value. This conclusion aligns with the study conducted by Hamzah, et al (2023) which found that relative advantage have no considerable impact on cloud accounting adoption in Indonesia. In addition, Chen, et al (2023) also stated that relative advantage does not have a significant positive effect on cloud computing adoption in China. Thus, although 'mobile banking' offers a number of advantages, younger generations who are already familiar with the digital ecosystem are likely to prioritize convenience and speed over feature differences.

The results also support findings in cross-country studies, which show that the effectiveness of factors in technology adoption models such as UTAUT and DOI is strongly influenced by social, cultural and institutional contexts. In some Middle Eastern countries that have low levels of public trust in digital institutions, perceived trust is still a dominant factor in driving adoption (Yaseen et al., 2022). In contrast, in Indonesia, high public trust in financial institutions and national banking regulations encourage users to focus more on functional aspects, such as ease of use and service performance (Nugroho et al., 2023). In addition, Bank Indonesia's policy of encouraging digital transformation through increasing financial inclusion also strengthens the development of more adaptive digital banking services. Therefore, strategies to increase 'mobile banking' adoption should not only focus on technological aspects, but also consider cultural dynamics, demographic characteristics, and local policy support that influence the behavior of generation Z in Indonesia.

Conclusion

The development of technology in the increasingly modern financial sector encourages the innovation of banking services into the digital era such as 'mobile banking' services. 'Mobile banking' is a digital banking innovation that allows customers to conduct transactions through mobile devices anytime and anywhere efficiently. Nonetheless, the embrace of 'mobile banking' in Indonesia remains suboptimal. Hence, this research seeks to explore the diverse elements that affect the willingness of Gen Z consumers to embrace 'mobile banking'. The results show that effort expectancy, performance expectancy, and

facilitating conditions have a significant influence on intention to use ‘mobile banking’. In contrast, perceived trust, perceived security, and relative advantage do not have a significant influence on intention to use ‘mobile banking’.

This research explains the theoretical and practical contributions. Theoretically, this study broadens the insights into the factors that influence intention to use ‘mobile banking’. First, this study extends the UTAUT model by adding perceived trust and perceived security factors that have not been widely studied in the intention to use ‘mobile banking’. Although both variables did not show a significant effect, this finding provides new insights that Generation Z in Indonesia has a high level of comfort and trust in digital technology, so that security and trust aspects are no longer the dominant factors in making decisions to use ‘mobile banking’. Second, this research employs the DOI framework to examine how relative advantage impact the intent to adopt ‘mobile banking’. The DOI study in this research shows that although relative advantage is an important aspect of technological innovation, the perception of this benefit is not strong enough to significantly drive the intention to use ‘mobile banking’ among Generation Z. The integration of these two theoretical approaches provides a more comprehensive perspective in explaining technology adoption behavior among digital generations such as Gen Z.

The research also outlines practical implications for digital banking in Indonesia to increase the adoption of ‘mobile banking’ among Generation Z. First, banks need to focus the development of ‘mobile banking’ services on the aspects of ease of use, reliable service performance, and the availability of supporting infrastructure such as internet networks and adequate technical assistance. This can be realized with an easy-to-understand application display, easily accessible features, and providing clear and easy to understand usage guidelines. Secondly, while security and trust remain important, the results show that for Generation Z, who are accustomed to digital technology, these factors are no longer the main drivers in the decision to use ‘mobile banking’. Therefore, the marketing strategy and development of digital services should emphasize efficiency, flexibility, and continuous user experience. Third, for customers, especially generation Z, the results of this study emphasize the importance of access to banking services that are not only fast and efficient, but also in line with their digital lifestyle. Fulfilling these needs will increase customer satisfaction, strengthen their loyalty, and encourage more active and sustainable use of digital services.

Although this study provides a lot of insight into the factors that influence intention to use ‘mobile banking’ in generation Z in Indonesia, there are several limitations that need to be considered. First, the use of nonprobability sampling methods may lead to sampling bias, which limits the generalizability of the results to the entire generation Z population. The unbalanced proportion of respondents with the dominance of female respondents at 78.4% has the potential to influence the interpretation of certain variables, especially perceived trust and perceived security, which according to several previous studies, namely Ahmed, et al (2024) and Xu, et al (2025) can be moderated by gender. Second, this study only uses quantitative data, which may not be able to explore in depth aspects related to the motivations and barriers experienced by users in adopting ‘mobile banking’. Third, this study is cross-sectional, so it cannot capture changes in user behavior over a

period of time, which may be influenced by technological developments or changing banking policies.

For future research, it is recommended to use a more representative and gender-balanced sampling method, given the limitations in this study dominated by female respondents (78.4%) which can lead to interpretation bias. Techniques such as stratified sampling or quota sampling can be used to ensure a fairer distribution and improve the generalizability of the results. In addition, a mixed methodology approach that combines quantitative and qualitative analysis may provide a more comprehensive understanding of the motivations, barriers, and psychosocial context of ‘mobile banking’ usage. To address the social bias in self-reporting that often arises in perception-based surveys, future research could also apply triangulation techniques, such as incorporating observational data or in-depth interviews for comparison. Furthermore, a longitudinal research design is recommended to examine changes in adoption behavior over time, along with technological developments and changes in banking policies. From a practical perspective, these results provide strategic insights for banks to provide digital services that are easily accessible, efficient and suited to Gen Z preferences, and for young customers to understand the benefits of these services more optimally, thereby increasing sustainable adoption. By addressing these limitations, future research is expected to provide deeper, more accurate and applicable insights in understanding the factors that influence ‘mobile banking’ adoption, and help service providers design more effective and sustainable strategies.

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